

Orthodontic Considerations For Tooth Agenesis : A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Tooth agenesis is one of the most prevalent dental developmental anomalies, commonly affecting the upper front teeth and both upper and lower premolars. Its causes are complex and include a mix of genetic, environmental, and epigenetic influences. This condition may be associated with syndromes such as ectodermal dysplasia or may occur in non-syndromic familial patterns. The absence of teeth can significantly impact bite alignment, appearance, chewing efficiency, and emotional well being.

Managing tooth agenesis orthodontically demands a team based approach that integrates accurate diagnosis, strategic treatment planning, and coordination with restorative and prosthodontic specialists. Clinical choices are guided by factors such as the number and position of missing teeth, the patient's age, growth stage, and the health of surrounding teeth. Treatment may involve either closing the spaces through orthodontic tooth movement or opening spaces to accommodate future prosthetic solutions like implants, bridges, or dentures. For younger patients who are still growing, temporary space maintainers may be used until they are ready for permanent treatment. A collaborative, interdisciplinary strategy is key to achieving optimal function and aesthetics. Detecting the condition early and initiating timely care is vital to reduce complications and ensure proper dental and facial development.

Keywords: Genetics, Orthodontic space management, Tooth agenesis

Introduction

Tooth agenesis is described as developmental absence of one or more teeth, occurring either in the primary or permanent dentition. It occurs after disruptions in the formation of tooth buds, which are critical to normal dental development. The condition poses significant clinical challenges, particularly when permanent teeth are congenitally missing. A central decision in managing these cases is either to close the space orthodontically or to restore it using prosthetic options, dental implants, or, in certain cases, auto-transplantation.¹

Tooth agenesis is classified by the number of missing teeth: hypodontia involves the absence of one to five teeth (excluding third molars); oligodontia refers to the absence of six or more teeth; and anodontia, a rare condition, is the complete absence of all teeth. While anodontia and syndromic oligodontia are often linked to systemic conditions like ectodermal dysplasia or Down syndrome, oligodontia can also appear as a non-

syndromic, isolated anomaly.²

Epidemiological data indicate a higher prevalence of dental agenesis in European and Australian populations compared to North American Caucasians, with females generally more affected than males. Females are nearly 1.37 times more likely to be affected by this condition, highlighting a potential gender based genetic component.³

Effective management requires early diagnosis, careful assessment of skeletal and dental development, and individualized treatment planning. A multidisciplinary approach involving orthodontists, prosthodontists, and other specialists is required to achieve both functional and aesthetic outcomes for patients with tooth agenesis.³

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According to Butler's Field Theory:

- Maxillary Lateral Incisors: It is one of the most prevalent form.
- Mandibular Incisors: Particularly the mandibular right lateral incisor.
- Permanent Molars: Agenesis of third molars is also commonly observed.⁴

Tooth agenesis can be categorised as:

1. Selective Tooth Agenesis: Involves specific teeth like lateral incisors.
2. Syndromic Tooth Agenesis: Associated with genetic disorders like ectodermal dysplasia, cleft lip and palate, or Van der Woude syndrome.
3. Non syndromic Tooth Agenesis: Occurs independently of other physical abnormalities.
4. Sporadic Tooth Agenesis: Occurs randomly without a familial pattern.⁵

Etiology

Environmental

Several factors are related to the etiology of tooth agenesis. Evolutionary changes in human dentition have contributed to a reduction in dental arch length, possibly leading to congenital absence of certain teeth as part of an adaptive mechanism. During tooth development, localized infections or inflammatory processes may disrupt endocrine activity, which in turn could be linked to ectodermal dysplasia a condition often associated with severe tooth agenesis. Environmental factors also play a role; for instance, exposure to teratogenic substances such as thalidomide, as well as chemotherapy or radiotherapy. While general maternal health during pregnancy does not appear to have a direct correlation with the development of hypodontia, specific infections like rubella have been identified as potential contributors to tooth agenesis in the fetus. Although tobacco and alcohol use have been proposed as possible risk factors, current evidence does not establish a definitive link between these exposures and the occurrence of hypodontia.⁶

Genetics

1. Although more than 300 genes have been implicated in odontogenesis in murine models, the precise molecular mechanisms governing human tooth development remain only partially understood. Genetic studies have identified several genes that contribute to tooth formation and, when mutated, may lead to tooth agenesis. Among these, mutations in *MSX1*, *PAX9*, *AXIN2*, *TGFA*, *IRF6*, *WNT10A*, and *FGFR1* have been associated with disrupted dental development. However, only three genes *MSX1*, *PAX9*, and *AXIN2* have been conclusively linked to familial, non-syndromic, autosomal dominant forms of tooth agenesis.⁷
2. The transcription factors *MSX1* (Muscle Segment Homeobox 1) and *PAX9* (Paired Box 9) are essential for early stages of facial and dental formation. Genetic mutations in these genes

are frequently linked to inherited cases of tooth agenesis, particularly affecting several back teeth like molars and premolars. On the other hand, mutations in *AXIN2*, a gene involved in the Wnt signaling pathway, are associated with a broader and less region-specific pattern of missing teeth. This often includes the absence of several permanent teeth, though the upper central incisors are generally present. The differing patterns of tooth loss associated with specific gene mutations suggest that analyzing which teeth are missing can help identify the underlying genetic cause.⁸

3. People born with missing teeth often display changes in the size and shape of their remaining teeth for example, lateral incisors may appear peg shaped or smaller than normal. (Fig 2) These features are typically seen as partial expressions of the same genetic factors responsible for tooth agenesis. A peg shaped maxillary lateral incisor, for instance, might reflect a milder form of the same genetic mutation that could otherwise result in the complete absence of the tooth. The frequent association of missing teeth with peg shaped laterals reinforces the idea that both may arise from the same genetic variation, potentially due to differences in gene expression or penetrance.⁹
4. Tooth agenesis often occurs alongside other dental abnormalities, indicating a more widespread developmental disturbance rather than an isolated issue. Commonly associated conditions include taurodontism (enlarged pulp chambers), shortened tooth roots, ectopic eruption, microdontia, unusual tooth shapes, and enamel hypoplasia. This combination of anomalies supports the view that tooth agenesis may be part of a broader pattern of developmental instability. In cases of oligodontia (where many teeth are missing), taurodontism and reduced root length are particularly prevalent. These features may stem from underlying ectodermal defects or systemic disruptions during tooth development.¹⁰

Ectopic eruption of permanent teeth is most common dental anomaly occurring along with hypodontia. This may occur due to the absence of adjacent teeth that typically provide eruption guidance, leading to misdirected or displaced tooth positioning. Without these neighbouring teeth, the developing permanent teeth may deviate from their normal eruption paths. These associations further support the idea that hypodontia is part of a broader spectrum of developmental disturbances affecting both tooth formation and eruption patterns.¹¹

Figure 1: Child with missing upper lateral incisor and multiple teeth in lower arch

Figure 2: Mother with missing upper lateral incisor and peg shaped opposite lateral incisor

Tooth Agenesis and Family History

Tooth agenesis is known to have a strong hereditary basis, often following familial patterns of inheritance. (Fig1)When a child presents with congenitally missing teeth, it is not uncommon to find that one or both parents have experienced similar dental anomalies, although the number and specific teeth affected may differ among relatives due to variable expressivity and incomplete penetrance. In certain instances, tooth agenesis may be a feature of a broader genetic syndrome that is transmitted through generations. Therefore, a thorough evaluation of family dental history plays a vital role in the early identification and management of the condition. For families with a known history of tooth agenesis or syndromic conditions involving dental anomalies, genetic counseling can provide valuable insight, particularly in the context of family planning and assessing the risk of recurrence in future offspring.¹¹

Diagnosis

Clinical Examination

1. First sign of agenesis can be made by a radiograph in which no evidence of presence of tooth is seen.
2. The failure of lateral incisor or premolar on side to erupt compared to its counterpart
3. Absence of permanent teeth causes the primary tooth infra-occlusion.
4. As many as two thirds of individuals missing premolars exhibit infra-occlusion of the related primary molars.¹²

Definitive Diagnosis

Radiographic examination is the key diagnostic factor in determining the agenesis of tooth.

Management of Tooth Agenesis

Patients with congenitally missing teeth are treated orthodontically. Managing these spaces created is critical not only for aesthetic concerns but also for ensuring proper long-term function. Orthodontists must carefully evaluate whether to close or maintain/open spaces, based on what will best benefit the patient's overall dental health and appearance. Extraction of retained deciduous teeth may be indicated to facilitate the natural migration of adjacent teeth where permanent teeth are absent.

Decision for extracting a retained primary tooth largely depends on its prognosis.¹³ If the tooth is healthy and stable, it may be retained to preserve space and alveolar bone for future restorative treatments. Conversely, extraction is advisable when the tooth is severely decayed or has a poor prognosis, with

subsequent orthodontic intervention to manage the space.¹⁴

Several key factors determine whether orthodontic treatment should aim to close or maintain space in cases of tooth agenesis. These include the presence of gaps or rotated teeth near the missing tooth site, which often need to be corrected before considering prosthetic solutions. The quantity and quality of alveolar bone in the affected area also play a critical role, as they influence both the potential for tooth movement and the suitability for dental implants. Another crucial factor is the vertical position of any retained primary molar in relation to the occlusal plane, which can impact the overall treatment plan. Ultimately, the decision-making process involves a thorough evaluation of the patient's bite alignment, facial structure, growth potential, degree of dental crowding, smile aesthetics, and tooth shape to determine the most appropriate orthodontic strategy.¹⁵

Space Opening Orthodontically

Patients with Angle's Class I malocclusion are generally ideal candidates for space opening. Cases presenting with upright maxillary incisors requiring proclination or those with anterior cross bites are also suited for space opening. Conversely, patients exhibiting bimaxillary protrusion or a convex soft tissue profile are typically poor candidates for this approach, making space closure a more appropriate option.

When managing congenitally missing maxillary lateral incisors, treatment planning often incorporates the principles of the Golden Proportion. This principle states that the perceived mesiodistal width of an anterior tooth should follow a ratio of approximately 1:0.618 relative to its adjacent tooth. Specifically, the lateral incisor's width should be about 61.8% that of the central incisor. This guideline is most applicable in cases of unilateral lateral incisor agenesis but may be challenging when the contralateral lateral incisor is peg-shaped, hypoplastic, or worn.¹⁶

Bolton analysis provides critical insight into tooth size relationships, with an ideal anterior tooth width ratio of 0.78 (sum of mandibular anterior widths to maxillary anterior widths). Additionally, a diagnostic wax-up can be valuable in predicting the optimal space required for prosthetic replacement.

In the mandibular arch, deciduous molars are often preserved to maintain alveolar bone and prevent arch length discrepancies. Slenderization (interproximal reduction) may be performed to manage space and alignment, while hemisection of a deciduous molar can be considered in select cases.

Following orthodontic space management, prosthodontic rehabilitation proceeds, with the timing of restorations largely dependent on the patient's skeletal maturity to ensure optimal outcomes

The treatment approach for tooth agenesis varies depending on the number of missing teeth and their functional and aesthetic impact. Common management strategies include:

- **Dental Implants and Bridges:** For patients missing a limited number of teeth, fixed prosthetic options such as dental implants or bridges are often preferred to restore both function and appearance.
- **Orthodontic Treatment:** Particularly important in younger patients, orthodontics helps align existing teeth and creates or maintains adequate space for future prosthetic replacements.
- **Dentures:** In cases of extensive tooth loss, removable partial or complete dentures may be necessary to restore oral function and aesthetics.
- **Multidisciplinary Care:** When tooth agenesis is part of a broader genetic syndrome, comprehensive care involving multiple specialists including geneticists, orthodontists, prosthodontists, and paediatric dentists is essential for holistic management.
- **Oral Health Maintenance:** Regardless of treatment modality, meticulous oral hygiene practices are vital to prevent secondary dental problems and ensure the longevity of restorations.¹⁶
- **Regular Dental Follow-up:** Ongoing dental evaluations are crucial to monitor oral health, assess growth and development, and promptly address any complications associated with tooth agenesis.

Figure 3: Missing both the upper lateral incisors. Replacement of the missing teeth by orthodontically opening the spaces

Orthodontic Space Closure

In cases of congenitally missing lateral incisors, the adjacent canines often erupt more mesially, naturally occupying the lateral incisor position. This spontaneous tooth migration eliminates the need for future prosthetic replacements, as the canine moves within the alveolar bone, helping to preserve both the bone volume and soft tissue architecture. Importantly, the gingival and periodontal tissues remain largely unaltered, supporting long-term periodontal health.¹⁷

However, orthodontic space closure with canine substitution has some limitations. The canine typically has a greater mesiodistal width than a lateral incisor, necessitating reshaping to achieve an esthetically acceptable form. In contrast, the premolars, which may substitute for canines, are generally wider both incisogingivally and mesiodistally, requiring more extensive recontouring and often the addition of a palatal cusp build up to mimic canine function and anatomy. Additionally, the gingival margin levels differ between canines and lateral incisors; therefore, the canine must be extruded slightly, while the

premolar is typically intruded to harmonize the gingival contour and achieve a balanced smile line.¹⁸

Figure 4: Missing both the upper canines. Orthodontically closing the spaces by mesialising the premolars.

Conclusion

Tooth agenesis is a developmental dental condition characterized by the absence of one or more teeth, with severity ranging from a single missing tooth to complete tooth loss. This anomaly can have a considerable impact on oral function, appearance, and overall dental well being. While hereditary factors are the most common cause, environmental elements and syndromic conditions can also play significant roles in its onset. Successful management involves a thorough understanding of the condition, routine dental evaluations, and coordinated care among dental professionals, including orthodontists and prosthodontists. Treatment strategies should be tailored to each individual, often combining orthodontic correction, prosthetic restoration, and, when needed, genetic consultation. Educating patients and their families is crucial to support informed choices and encourage active involvement in the treatment process. Although tooth agenesis presents certain clinical challenges, well timed, personalized care can help individuals maintain good oral health and quality of life. Moreover, ongoing progress in dental technologies and regenerative medicine offers promising future solutions for improving treatment outcomes.

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